

Ship inspection report

1. Purpose and task of the test:

Experimenting with the shape of a hybrid-powered water-bicycle float.

Another goal is to make a proposal to the designer to design the final construction based on the experimental results.

Basically, we compare two different shipbuilding constructions:

a, A flat-bottomed structure in which the entire bottom of the vessel is typically in contact with the water surface,

b, Catamaran physique, with 2 pcs. a narrower float is in contact with the water surface, but the central area of the vessel is not. Smaller surface support results in greater immersion depth.

2. Technical description of the test hull forms to be tested:

a, The flat-bottomed construction was constructed with a slightly arched nose pattern and a straight, flat tail mirror. At the bottom of the hull there are longitudinal guide ribs that help to steer the boat as well as ensure optimal water flow.

Technical data:

Length: 5.55 m

Width: 1.88 m

Height: 0.72 m

Weight: 215 kg

Waterline length: 4.95 m

Dive empty: 0.11 m

Dive with 1 person load: 0.13 m

Dive with 2 main loads: 0.14 m

Dive with 3 main loads: 0.14 m

Dive with 4 people load: 0.15 m

Extreme situations of center of gravity migration:

No load: measured from a 2.3 m mirror

In case of 2 frontal loads: measured from a mirror of 2.63 m

2 main loads at the rear: measured from a mirror of 1,97 m

Center of gravity migration: 0.66 m

Hull construction materials:

Made of colored fiberglass-reinforced resin hull with built-in wood reinforcements.

b., A separate float with a small radius at each end of the catamaran structure. The connecting beams were made of wood.

Specifications:

Length: 5.15 m

Width: 1.85 m

Height: 0.82 m

Weight: 152 kg

Waterline length: 5.05 m

Dive empty: 0.09 m

Dive with 1 person load: 0.14 m

Dive with 2 main loads: 0.14 m

Dive with 3 main loads: 0.17 m

Dive with 4 main loads: 0.17 m

Extreme situations of center of gravity migration

No load: 2.50 m measured from the tip of the tail

In case of 2 main front loads: 2.86 m measured from the tail tip

For 2 main loads at the rear: 2.14 m measured from the tail tip

Center of gravity migration: 0.72 m

3. Test conditions

The experimental hulls shall be inspected according to the following criteria:

a., Load conditions

5.a.1., In front of 1 person,

5.a.2, in front of 2 people,

5.a.3, 2 people in front, 1 person in the back,

5.a.4, 2 people in front, 2 people in the back,

5.a.5, 2 people in the back,

5.a.6, 2 people in the back, 1 person in front,

5.a.7, 1 person in the back.

b., Wind speed conditions

0 m / s

2 - 3 m / s

4 - 5 m / s

c., Water wave sizes

Flat water: 0 - 10 mm waves

Slight undulation: 10 - 50 mm waves

Stronger corrugation: 50 - 100 mm waves

d., Performance data:

The direct propulsion element of the experimental hulls is the electric marine engine.

In the final prototype, the engine's built-in power control electronic system will be installed in its original, unaltered form. Thus, the motor power can be controlled indefinitely within the available range.

During the experimental measurements, the engine power is adjusted to 25, 50, 75 and 100% power and the test is repeated with each data set.

6., Testing equipment:

a., Large-scale digital balance for measuring the mass of experimental hulls.

b., Supporting pendulum to determine the center of gravity of the experimental hulls.

c., GPS. system speed measuring device for measuring speed data.

d., Stopwatch to measure driving time on the designated 50 m section of track.

e., Wind speed meter to measure wind conditions

f., Tape measure to determine wave sizes and dive values and to designate a 50 m track.

7., Tables of measurement results

For Experimental 1 (flat bottom) hull

Table 1 / a: Speed km / h (0 m / s wind, 0-10 mm wave)

Table 1 / b: Speed km / h (2-3 m / s tailwind, 10-50 mm wave)

Table 1 / c: Speed km / h (2-3 m / s headwind, 10-50 mm wave)

Table 1 / d: Speed Km / h (2-3 m / s side wind 10-50 mm wave)

Table 1 / e: Speed Km / h (4-5 m / s tailwind, 50-100 mm wave)

Table 1 / f: Speed Km / h (4-5 m / s headwind, 50-100 mm wave)

Table 1 / g: Speed Km / h (4-5 m / s side wind, 50-100 mm wave)

For Experimental 2 (catamaran system) hull

Table 2 / a: Speed km / h (0 m / s wind, 0-10 mm wave)

Table 2 / b: Speed km / h (2-3 m / s tailwind, 10-50 mm wave)

Table 2 / c: Speed km / h (2-3 m / s headwind, 10-50 mm wave)

Table 2 / d: Speed Km / h (2-3 m / s side wind 10-50 mm wave)

Table 2 / e: Speed Km / h (4-5 m / s tail wind, 50-100 mm wave)

Table 2 / f: Speed Km / h (4-5 m / s headwind, 50-100 mm wave)

Table 2 / g: Speed Km / h (4-5 m / s side wind, 50-100 mm wave)

The tables contain the values of the measured speeds with the selected load and motor power data under the listed external conditions.

8., The result of the research

Based on the measurement data, it can be stated that the speed data of the experimental hull with a catamaran system marked "Experimental-2" is more favorable, this is especially noticeable in the 75 and 100% engine power ranges. In windless weather, the Experimental-2 showed an average speed deviation of 10% at 25 and 50% engine power, however, at 75 and 100% engine power, the deviation averaged 23% in favor of Experimental-2. At 5 m / s wind speed and 100 mm wave height, at 25 and 50% engine power, the average deviation was 21%, while at 75 and 100% engine power, the average difference was already 52% in favor of Experimental-2.

Different water ripples also have less of an effect on performance values with this system. The Experimental-2 hull is less sensitive to crosswinds, has better heading, and has less speed due to crosswinds. The ship's maneuverability by turning the engine hull is much more efficient than the Experimental-1 hull, but with the Experimental-2 hull, this disadvantage can be overcome by steering surfaces mounted at the end of the hulls. This solution makes governance efficient.